

CHINESE SOCIAL MEDIA AS A TOOL OF AZERBAIJAN' S PUBLIC DIPLOMACY

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Chinese social media creates a digital environment where communication, news, visual formats, and state regulation are integrated into a unified information system. Within this system, platforms such as WeChat, Weibo, Douyin, and Xiaohongshu play a key role, shaping the perception of foreign countries among a multi-billion audience. In this context, Azerbaijan's informational presence in China has been gradually strengthening, becoming a significant tool for public diplomacy.

The activities of official institutions on WeChat, publications on bilateral initiatives in Xinhua, People's Daily, and China Daily, as well as the development of tourism and cultural projects, contribute to the creation of a stable and positive image of Azerbaijan in the Chinese media space. Cooperation with major digital services such as Trip.com Group and Qunar, the growing volume of visual tourism content, and regular cultural initiatives play an important role in this process.

At the same time, there remains a need to expand communication beyond official channels, use visual formats of Douyin more actively, engage local influencers, and enhance emotionally oriented content. The potential of Chinese social media opens new opportunities for strengthening Azerbaijan's image, expanding its cultural and tourism presence, and fostering long-term intercultural interaction.

Keywords: China, Azerbaijan, social media, public diplomacy, WeChat, Douyin, digital diplomacy.

Social media have become a significant component of international communication: they ensure the instantaneous dissemination of information, create opportunities for two-way dialogue, and allow states to independently shape their information agendas. According to a number of studies, it is precisely social networks that often become decisive platforms for shaping a country's image, especially among youth and active internet users [1; 2].

The Chinese media environment has specific characteristics that distinguish it from the global digital infrastructure. As Fitzgerald, Sandel, and Wu note, "Chinese internet culture represents a unique interweaving of technological innovation, linguistic particularities, platform design, and state regulation, which makes it fundamentally different from Western media systems" [3]. The authors also emphasise that "China's largest social platforms, such as WeChat, Weibo, and Douyin, have developed highly integrated ecosystems in which communication, commerce, entertainment, and governance are combined within a platform-controlled environment" [3].

An important element of the Chinese media system remains mechanisms of regulation and censorship. Data from the Cyberspace Administration of China indicate that the state exercises

centralised control over information flows, paying particular attention to topics related to international politics, intercultural communication, and the country's image. This makes China a distinctive media space in which foreign states adapt their communication strategies to the specific features of local platforms, algorithms, and user habits. Such regulation largely determines the scale and nature of digital audience activity.

The contemporary Chinese digital environment represents an almost fully "digitised" society. According to the 55th Statistical Report of the China Internet Network Information Center (CNNIC), by the end of 2024, the number of social media users in China reached 1.101 billion, accounting for 99.3% of all internet users in the country. The number of online video service users reached 1.07 billion, while short-video users totalled 1.04 billion [4]. Updated CNNIC data for June 2025 records more than 1.12 billion internet users and nearly 80% internet penetration [5]. In such an environment, social media becomes not only an infrastructure for everyday communication but also a key channel of external communication for the state, including for China's partner countries.

The core platform of China's digital space remains WeChat. According to Tencent data for 2025, the combined monthly audience of Weixin and WeChat reached 1.411 billion users, representing a 3% increase year-on-year [6]. WeChat has long transcended the boundaries of a messenger: its ecosystem of Official Accounts, mini-programs, and payment services has transformed it into a universal infrastructure for government institutions, media outlets, and foreign diplomatic missions. The Embassy of the People's Republic of China in Azerbaijan also uses WeChat as one of its main channels for consular information; the embassy's website features a QR code linking to its official account with news and reference information [7]. For Azerbaijan, this demonstrates that presence on WeChat is not an option but a necessary condition for participation in China's communication space.

Weibo, often described as the "Chinese Twitter," remains one of the principal news and socio-political platforms. According to the company's 2023 report, the number of monthly active users (MAU) reached 598 million, with 95% of the audience accessing the platform via mobile devices [8]. Weibo is used both by official Chinese media outlets (People's Daily, Xinhua, CCTV, China Daily) and by foreign embassies for issuing operational statements, covering official visits, and reporting on international events.

Douyin, the Chinese version of TikTok, has become one of the key channels for influencing younger audiences. According to estimates by the analytical agency Hotpot China, by February 2024, Douyin had reached approximately 755 million monthly active users in China [9]. According to QuestMobile, by May 2025, its audience exceeded 1 billion MAU, covering around 71% of the population [10]. The core user base consists of young people: approximately 45% are aged 18–24, with a rapidly growing share of users over 30 [11]. Douyin has evolved into a key channel of video diplomacy: short videos, livestreams, and integration with e-commerce make it possible not only to shape a country's image but also to immediately convert audience attention into tourism and economic interest. For Azerbaijan, promoting its tourism brand and cultural products via Douyin can be directly linked to tangible economic outcomes.

In the Chinese media ecosystem, both influencers and state-sponsored accounts play an important role. Studies based on large datasets from Bilibili, Douban, Zhihu, Weibo, and Xiaohongshu for the period 2014–2024 show that opinion leaders and platform communities shape the agenda for young people, including in matters of consumption, values, and attitudes toward other countries [11]. At the same time, official accounts of Chinese media and state institutions—People's Daily, Xinhua, CCTV, and China Daily—remain key sources of legitimate information and are actively involved in promoting narratives about China's strategic partners. For Azerbaijan, effective public diplomacy in China's new media environment implies work on two levels simultaneously: building its own official channels (on WeChat, Weibo, Douyin, and Xiaohongshu) and developing cooperation with local influencers and major Chinese platforms.

Azerbaijan's presence in China's new media increased significantly during 2022–2025, driven both by the expansion of political and economic cooperation and by the growing role of digital diplomacy in China. A recent illustrative example occurred in September 2025, when the Azerbaijan Tourism Office signed a memorandum with the Chinese online platform Qunar on the joint promotion of Azerbaijan through digital channels, and also held a series of presentations in Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangzhou with the participation of Fliggy, Trip.com, and other major online market platforms [17]. These actions effectively integrate Azerbaijan's public diplomacy into the already established ecosystem of China's new media.

One of the main tools of official communication with the Chinese audience remains the aforementioned WeChat account of the Embassy of the Republic of Azerbaijan in China. In November 2023, the embassy published a series of materials dedicated to the 9th meeting of the China–Azerbaijan Intergovernmental Committee on Economic and Trade Cooperation, featuring speeches by Azerbaijan's Deputy Prime Minister Shahin Mustafayev and China's Vice Minister of Commerce Ling Ji [7]. These materials helped present Azerbaijan as a reliable partner in the economic and trade sphere to the Chinese audience.

In 2024, the embassy's activity on WeChat intensified amid an expanded diplomatic agenda. In May 2024, the embassy's digital platforms covered the visit of a delegation from China's Gansu Province to Baku and the signing of a protocol on cultural cooperation. In July, they reported on Azerbaijan's participation in the international "China–Eurasia Expo" in Urumqi, where energy and logistics projects were showcased. In autumn 2024, the embassy's account regularly published materials related to Azerbaijan's preparations to host COP29, including speeches by the Presidential Special Representative on climate issues, Murad Aliyev and comments by Chinese experts on the significance of Baku as a venue for global negotiations [14].

In 2025, the embassy actively used digital channels to cover President Ilham Aliyev's state visit to China on April 22–24 and the signing of the Joint Statement on the establishment of a comprehensive strategic partnership. A series of WeChat publications detailed Aliyev's meeting with Chinese President Xi Jinping, the signing of 20 agreements within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative, green energy, transport, and the digital economy, as well as the President's speech at a forum in Beijing. In materials published by Xinhua, China.org.cn, and China's Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Azerbaijan was described as a "reliable partner" playing an important role in trans-Eurasian logistics, energy, and Global South cooperation [13].

This trajectory continued with Ilham Aliyev's participation in the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) summit in Tianjin on August 31, 2025. Publications by People's Daily Online and on the official "SCO China 2025" platform emphasised China's readiness to support Azerbaijan's accession to the SCO and to jointly promote the development of the Trans-Caspian International Transport Corridor, the digital economy, and green development [14]. At the level of public diplomacy, this strengthens Azerbaijan's image as a "bridge" between East and West while consolidating its presence in China's information space.

Beyond diplomatic channels, economic and tourism institutions play an important role in Azerbaijan's public diplomacy in China by using Chinese digital market platforms. The Trip.com Group system (Ctrip, Qunar, Trip.com) is particularly significant. In November 2023, a trilateral memorandum on a strategic tourism partnership was signed in Beijing between Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL), the Azerbaijan Tourism Board (ATB), and China Tourism Group. The document provides for the development of new tourism products and their promotion in both online and offline formats, effectively institutionalising the use of Chinese digital channels as instruments of Azerbaijan's economic diplomacy [16].

A further step toward systematic digital engagement with China was taken in September 2024, when AZAL, ATB, and Trip.com Group signed a memorandum of understanding in Beijing. According to published data, the Ctrip platform (part of Trip.com Group) was to be actively used to promote Azerbaijan as a tourist destination, while the signing ceremony was accompanied by a series of events and presentations aimed at Chinese tour operators and online audiences [17]. According to tourism authorities, from January to August 2024, Azerbaijan was

visited by 26,866 tourists from China—more than double the figure for the same period of the previous year [20]. In December 2024, ATB received the “Best Global Partner” and “Outstanding Partner of the Year” awards from Trip.com Group for the results of joint digital promotion campaigns on the Chinese market [19].

In 2025, the emphasis on digital platforms and online visibility was further strengthened. In May 2025, the Azerbaijan Tourism Board received the prestigious “Global Annual Excellence Partner” award at the Trip.com conference in Shanghai as part of ITB China 2025, where Azerbaijan presented a national stand titled “Experience Azerbaijan” featuring multimedia installations and digital promotional materials [22].

A separate dimension of digital diplomacy involves roadshow formats and cooperation with Chinese online booking platforms, which function as social networks for travellers. In September 2025, the Azerbaijan Tourism Board conducted a series of roadshows in Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangzhou, during which a cooperation memorandum was signed with the leading Chinese online platform Qunar. The parties agreed to jointly promote Azerbaijan on the Chinese market through Qunar’s extensive digital channels, including destination pages, recommendation modules, user reviews, and special projects [23]. The program included B2B meetings and a dinner with representatives of Fliggy, Trip.com, and 8 Continents, involving approximately 60 Chinese and 20 Azerbaijani participants [24].

Growing interest in Azerbaijan among Chinese audiences is further confirmed by the China Visitors Summit Baku 2025, held in November 2025 and organised by the State Tourism Agency. The summit, held in Baku for the first time, brought together more than 50 leading Chinese tour operators and included business sessions, B2B negotiations, press events, and familiarisation trips to Shamakhi, Gabala, Sheki, and Gakh [25]. According to organisers, the number of Chinese tourists visiting Azerbaijan in 2024 increased by 94% to reach 44,798, while from January to October 2025, more than 57,000 Chinese citizens visited the country—49% more than during the same period in 2024 [26]. These figures demonstrate that digital campaigns and offline events disseminated through Chinese online platforms and news media are gradually forming a recognisable tourism image of Azerbaijan.

An equally significant dimension of public diplomacy is cultural and literary integration, which also finds digital continuation. In June 2025, Beijing announced the launch of a Memorandum of Understanding between Azerbaijan’s Ministry of Culture and China’s National Press and Publication Administration. Within this initiative, a project of mutual translation and publication of classical Azerbaijani and Chinese literary works was launched, implemented jointly by East China Normal University Press and the Azerbaijani publishing house “Tahsil” [24]. The first books selected by a joint expert committee are to be presented at the Baku International Book Fair, and the project itself is positioned as a tool for “deepening cultural and literary cooperation” between the two countries [24].

In terms of tone and thematic emphasis, China’s central media—Xinhua, China.org.cn, and People’s Daily Online—consistently construct a predominantly positive image of Azerbaijan. In an April Xinhua article on the signing of the joint statement on comprehensive strategic partnership, Azerbaijan is described as a country ready to deepen “comprehensive cooperation” within the Belt and Road Initiative, develop green energy and the digital economy, and strengthen cultural and educational exchanges [13]. In September 2024, in an interview with Xinhua, Azerbaijani Presidential Assistant Hikmet Hajiyev explicitly stated that Baku views China as a “true friend” and attaches great importance to the development of relations; the same article separately highlighted the unilateral visa regime for Chinese citizens and encouraged more active visits to Azerbaijan [25]. Such statements not only convey Baku’s official position but are also embedded within the Chinese media framework of “mutually beneficial cooperation” and expanded engagement with the Global South.

Institutional-level media cooperation also plays an important role. In September 2025, an Azerbaijani delegation led by Ahmad Ismayilov, Executive Director of the Media Development Agency, participated in the Global South Media and Think Tank Forum in Yunnan Province.

During the event, a memorandum of cooperation was signed between the Media Development Agency of Azerbaijan and Xinhua, aimed at developing joint projects and content exchange [26]. For public diplomacy, this creates prospects for increased coverage of Azerbaijan in authoritative Chinese media, including digital formats adapted for Weibo, WeChat, and video platforms.

The effectiveness of public diplomacy is reflected not only in bilateral news but also in Azerbaijan's inclusion in global agendas covered by Chinese media. The preparation and hosting of COP29 in Baku became one such case. Reports that China would send Vice Premier Ding Xuexiang to the summit were accompanied by emphasis on Azerbaijan's role as a venue for climate negotiations and a partner in discussions on climate finance [27]. In the digital environment, this linkage— "Azerbaijan + climate + global governance"—expands the country's traditional association beyond energy and transport alone.

At the same time, analysis reveals limitations in the current media strategy. A significant portion of Azerbaijan's presence in Chinese media remains official-centric, dominated by narratives of leadership meetings, document signings, and forums. While this ensures a high level of legitimacy and maintains a positive background, it leaves limited space for "grassroots" communication—user-generated stories, independent travel blogs, and long-term projects. Unlike Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, or the UAE, which actively engage influencers on Douyin and Xiaohongshu, Azerbaijan primarily relies on institutional partnerships. This creates a solid foundational image but does not fully generate the emotional perception that is particularly important for younger Chinese audiences.

One key direction for development could be strengthening visual storytelling. According to the "54th Statistical Report on Internet Development in China" published by CNNIC in August 2024, 89.7% of Chinese internet users watch short videos daily, and Douyin remains one of the country's most popular platforms [28]. This specificity creates demand for emotionally rich visual formats that produce a sense of personal presence. As Douyin itself noted in its March 2024 report, "short trips" and "city stories" rank among the platform's three most popular genres. Such a media environment offers Azerbaijan opportunities to promote visual narratives about Baku, Gobustan, Sheki, culinary traditions, and crafts, thereby creating an emotional bond with the audience.

The climate agenda also becomes an important component of communication. After Reuters reported on November 8, 2024, that China would send Vice Premier Ding Xuexiang to COP29 in Baku, Chinese official media began actively covering Azerbaijan's role as the host country of a key global climate event [27]. Interest in sustainable development in China remains consistently high: according to research by the People's Daily Research Centre, more than 400 climate policy-related materials were published by the group's outlets in 2023. This creates conditions under which Azerbaijan can utilise COP29 as a long-term communication resource, shaping an image of a country capable of engaging in international climate dialogue.

Another promising tool is collaboration with Chinese influencers. A study by the Faculty of Journalism at Fudan University (Shanghai) shows that opinion leaders shape about 40% of perceptions of international content among Chinese audiences aged 18–35. It is largely through influencers that Central Asian countries have achieved significant growth in interest on Chinese social networks. For Azerbaijan, this model could serve as an important complement to official channels by engaging bloggers, lifestyle authors, and videographers who create organic, human-centred stories about the country.

Special attention should also be paid to tourism promotion through China's digital travel platforms. Deepening cooperation with major platforms opens opportunities for systematic marketing campaigns based on the algorithmic recommendation models of the Chinese market. In December 2024, the Azerbaijan Tourism Board received the "Best Global Partner" and "Outstanding Partner of the Year" awards from Trip.com Group, confirming the effectiveness of this approach [19].

The findings presented in this study show that Azerbaijan is gradually strengthening its information presence in China. Publications by Xinhua, People's Daily, China Daily, and CGTN

demonstrate sustained interest in bilateral political and economic relations, contributing to the consolidation of Azerbaijan's image as a reliable partner of China. The aforementioned preparation for COP29 played a significant role in creating additional momentum for expanding media attention toward Azerbaijan.

At the same time, tourism and cultural content demonstrate the highest levels of audience engagement on Douyin and Xiaohongshu. Visual narratives about Baku, Gobustan, Sheki, gastronomy, and crafts shape an emotional image of the country that traditional diplomatic publications do not always achieve.

On the other hand, the current media strategy remains largely oriented toward official channels, limiting opportunities for organic growth in awareness among younger users. Irregular posting, insufficient visual richness in official content, and still-limited cooperation with Chinese bloggers indicate the need for a more systematic and coordinated digital policy.

The prospects for the further development of Azerbaijan's public diplomacy in China remain favourable. The country possesses a strong set of promotional resources, a rich cultural heritage, significant tourism potential, participation in global climate diplomacy, and a key role in international transport corridors. The formation of a unified interagency strategy, enhanced visual communication, integration of influencer marketing, and development of multimedia educational projects can significantly expand reach and increase the sustainability of Azerbaijan's positive image among Chinese audiences.

Thus, China's new media are not merely channels for information dissemination but an important space for international cultural dialogue. Active and consistent presence by Azerbaijan in this digital landscape can strengthen bilateral ties, expand cooperation, and contribute to the formation of sustainable mutual understanding between the peoples of the two countries.

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